

The Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Occupational Burnout: A Cross-Sectional Study on Aviation Industry

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Article Info	Abstract
RESEARCH ARTICLE	<p>Since the concepts of job satisfaction and occupational burnout are closely related to each other, many studies have been conducted on employees in different sectors. This study aims to investigate the effect of occupational burnout on job satisfaction levels of aviation sector employees. For this purpose, between July 2019 and September 2023, data were collected from 202 aviation employees determined by convenience sampling method through questionnaire forms. The data of the study were subjected to correlation and regression analyses with SPSS 22 software. The results of the study show that as depersonalization and emotional burnout, which are the sub-dimensions of occupational burnout, increase, intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction of aviation sector employees decreases. In addition, another sub-dimension of occupational burnout, personal accomplishment, increases as intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction increases.</p>
<p>Keywords: Job satisfaction Occupational Burnout Aviation Sector SPSS 22</p>	
<p>Received: Oct., 30. 2023 Revised: Dec., 05. 2023 Accepted: Dec, 16. 2023</p>	

1. Introduction

The structures of enterprises are changing day by day. Businesses, which were previously established to meet the demand of customers for goods and services, have become able to produce in accordance with the demands and expectations of their customers with changing market conditions.

In an intense competitive environment where the number of enterprises has increased with globalization, businesses see human resources as an element that can make a difference among their competitors (Kurt and Bülbül, 2023; Keleş et al., 2023). At the same time, they aim to make their success sustainable by obtaining maximum profit with their investment in human resources. However, it is stated that the critical factor in achieving this goal is the job satisfaction of the employees (Çetintürk, 2017; Wang et al., 2008). The literature reveals that the productivity of individuals with a certain level of job satisfaction increases and therefore this positively affects business performance. However, the intense competitive environment in which businesses operate and the constant change in the demands and expectations of customers can create a serious pressure on businesses and employees. This pressure environment causes the concept of stress to become continuous and this situation may cause burnout in employees over time.

Burnout refers to situations such as emotional burnout, Depersonalization and low sense of achievement that occur because of the individual's inability to cope with occupational stress. This process occurs due to intense stress in the work environment. Over time, the individual becomes alienated from his/her job, becomes callous,

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and experiences a sense of failure. Failure to recognize burnout early can cause negative effects for both the individual and the organization. As a result of burnout, the contribution of the employee to the business may decrease and as a result, business efficiency is negatively affected (Yılmaz, 2020; Çavuş et al., 2007; Çöbek, 2010; Ülbeği, 2016). This study aims to investigate the effect of occupational burnout of aviation sector employees on their job satisfaction levels. With this motivation, the study seeks answers to the next research question.

- What is the effect of occupational burnout on job satisfaction of employees working in organizations operating in the aviation sector?

The study has the following structure: The second section presents a literature review on job satisfaction and occupational burnout. The third section explains the research methodology. While the fourth section presents the main discoveries, the last section provides a discussion of the results and concludes the study.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Job satisfaction

The levels of job satisfaction have an important impact on employee happiness, motivation, and productivity. Elevated job satisfaction fosters a positive attitude towards work, prompting employees to willingly contribute their best efforts for the benefit of the business. Conversely, low levels of job satisfaction may result in apathy, adaptation issues, and a sense of alienation from their roles (Günay, 2016: 22). Job dissatisfaction can have adverse effects not only on individuals but also on organizations. According to Tunceli (2012: 59), negative work-related behaviors, such as reluctance to attend work, making mistakes, feeling inadequate, a desire to escape work, absenteeism, and damage to equipment, may occur.

Various perspectives have been employed to analyze the personal factors contributing to job satisfaction, including age, educational background, personality traits, gender, work experience (seniority), skills, marital status, intelligence, and socio-cultural environment. As Uç (2016) points out, an individual's attitudes and behaviors can be shaped by the environment in which they were raised and currently reside. According to Somuncuoğlu (2013), job satisfaction may decline in both individual and organizational contexts. It's crucial to recognize that satisfaction levels differ between jobs requiring high-level skills and routine jobs. High-level jobs tend to be more satisfying as they offer employees a sense of accomplishment. Çakmak Doruk (2008) suggests that female employees may experience work-family conflict and a decrease in job satisfaction if their responsibilities increase after marriage and their spouses cannot provide sufficient assistance. Several studies have explored the impact of gender on job satisfaction (Eğinli, 2009; Sat, 2011; Çiftıldız, 2015), but there is no consensus on which gender is more satisfied with their job. Research indicates that job satisfaction varies between genders, with some studies showing higher satisfaction levels among men and others among women. This variation may be influenced by factors such as the industry in which the research is conducted and company policies (Eğinli, 2009: 39).

2.2. Occupational Burnout

Job satisfaction is a concept that can have personal, physiological, and psychological effects on individuals. If an individual is dissatisfied with their job, negative thoughts can gradually develop. These negative thoughts can result in adverse impacts on both material and spiritual aspects, as well as mental and physical health. As a consequence, individuals may lose interest in their job, become less attentive, and may even contemplate quitting, leading to job dissatisfaction and eventual burnout (Parlar, 2008: 552). Research has presented conflicting perspectives on whether job satisfaction influences burnout or if burnout affects job satisfaction (Gürbüz, 2008: 35). Employees facing job dissatisfaction are susceptible to burnout, which can have detrimental consequences for both the individual and the organization (Kalkizoğlu, 2018: 9).

Maslach and Jackson (1981) are acknowledged as pioneers in burnout research and formulated a model to examine the subject. They described burnout as a syndrome characterized by emotional exhaustion, anger, cynicism, and depersonalization, commonly observed in individuals who work face-to-face with people. The concept of burnout comprises three primary factors: depersonalization, emotional exhaustion and a low sense of personal accomplishment (Çöbek, 2010: 6). Burnout, in its most prevalent form, is described as a syndrome arising from physical exhaustion, prolonged fatigue, feelings of helplessness and despair in individuals who confront intense emotional demands in their job and must consistently interact with others, leading to negative disposition towards work, people and life (Maslach & Jackson, 1981). The factors contributing to burnout may

vary from person to person. This article explores burnout and its potential causes, including personality structure (Akçamete, Kaner, & Sucuoğlu, 2001; Çağlıyan, 2007; Sürgevil Dalkılıç, 2014), expectations (Karadağ, 2013; Kalkızıoğlu, 2018; Berber, 2011; Skeja, 2012), lack of self-sufficiency (Tunceli, 2012; Sürgevil Dalkılıç, 2014), External Control Orientation (Dalkılıç, 2014; Berber, 2011), and demographic characteristics (Tümkiye, 1996; Yıldırım, 1996; Buick & Thomas, 2001; Ok, 2002; Yücel, 2012; Akbulut, 2010; Tunceli, 2012).

2.3 The relationship between Job Satisfaction and Occupational Burnout

When the concepts of job satisfaction and occupational burnout are considered together, a negative relationship is observed between these two concepts. Job satisfaction influences the dimension of depersonalization, which is one of the sub-dimensions of occupational burnout. In addition to individual characteristics such as gender, age, marital status, and education level, various environmental and organizational factors, such as job conditions and the nature of the work, also affect job satisfaction. However, definite conclusions are not applicable to each variable in this regard. Individuals who are not content with their jobs face burnout, and this situation leads to some negative consequences for both themselves and their organizations (Kalkızıoğlu, 2018: 9).

According to the related literature, the hypotheses determined within the framework of the research questions are as below. In the study, occupational burnout sub-dimensions were determined as independent variables and job satisfaction sub-dimensions were determined as dependent variables. Figure 1 shows the research model of the study.

Figure 1. Research model

H1a: There is a significant relationship between emotional exhaustion and internal satisfaction.

H1b: There is a significant relationship between emotional exhaustion and external satisfaction.

H2a: There is a significant relationship between depersonalization and internal satisfaction.

H2b: There is a significant relationship between depersonalization and external satisfaction.

H3a: There is a significant relationship between the personal accomplishment level and internal satisfaction.

H3b: There is a significant relationship between personal accomplishment level and external satisfaction.

H4a: Emotional exhaustion significantly effects internal satisfaction.

H4b: Emotional exhaustion significantly effects external satisfaction.

H4c: Depersonalization significantly effects internal satisfaction.

H4d: Depersonalization significantly effects external satisfaction.

H4e: Personal accomplishment has a significant effect on internal satisfaction.

H4f: Personal accomplishment has a significant effect on external satisfaction.

3. Methodology

3.1. Sampling and data collection

This research aims to evaluate the potential relationship between occupational burnout levels and job satisfaction of employees in the aviation industry. For this purpose, the study was conducted on aviation sector employees who working in the aviation sector in Turkey. In the research, survey applications, which are expressed as primary data collection sources, were utilized. The questionnaires were collected by face-to-face and online data collection method, on a completely voluntary basis and with the declaration that the data will not be shared with any institution and person. Data were collected through questionnaire forms to the participants selected using convenience sampling method between July 2019 and September 2019. Within the scope of the research, a total of 202 participants returned with fully completed questionnaire forms.

3.2. Instruments

Personal information form was used to obtain demographic information of the aviation sector employees constituting the sample of the study. In addition, a questionnaire with a total of 48 questions, including the Maslach Burnout Scale to assess the occupational burnout levels of the participants and the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale to measure their job satisfaction, was applied. In the selection of the scales in the questionnaires, it was thought that the sub-dimensions of the scales could respond to the problem of the research. Minnesota job satisfaction scale comprise of external and internal satisfaction sub-dimensions, and Maslach burnout scale comprise of depersonalization, emotional exhaustion and sense of personal accomplishment sub-dimensions.

Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale: Baycan (1985) adapted the job satisfaction scale developed by Dawis, Weis, England, and Lofquist in 1967 for use in Turkish. A reliability and validity study was conducted and the reliability value (Cronbach's Alpha) was found to be 0.77. Minnesota is a five-point Likert scale, with scores ranging from 1 to 5. The survey consists of a total of 20 questions that measure the overall job satisfaction of employees and includes individual (internal) and organisational (external) job satisfaction sub-dimensions.

The individual (internal) satisfaction dimension consists of items related to satisfaction with the internal quality of the job, such as achievement, recognition or appreciation, the job itself, the responsibility of the job, promotion and job change due to promotion. The scores obtained from the items in this dimension are divided by 12 to obtain the individual job satisfaction score. The Organisational (External) Satisfaction dimension consists of items related to the working environment, such as company policy and management, supervisory style, relationships with superiors and subordinates, working conditions, pay. Organisational job satisfaction was calculated by dividing the sum of the ratings from the questions in this dimension by 8. The range of ratings that define job satisfaction can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Job Satisfaction Levels

High	Medium	Low
3.35 and above	1,68 – 3,34	0 – 1,67

Maslach Burnout Survey: In Turkey, Maslach Burnout Scale has been preferred in most of the studies conducted to measure employees' sense of burnout. In this study, the 22-question Maslach Burnout Questionnaire, which was adapted into Turkish by Ergin (1992), was used. The original form of the questionnaire includes 7 Likert response options. In the Turkish version of the questionnaire, 5 Likert response options such as "never, very rarely, sometimes, most of the time, always" were used in this study.

In the factor analysis used to assess the construct validity of the scale, 5 natural factors initially emerged. These were found to be grouped into 3 sub-dimensions. Varimax rotation was used to re-evaluate the results. This led to the conclusion that burnout consists of three dimensions: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment. High levels of burnout are indicated by high scores on this scale. The responses to the questions were rated on a scale of 0-4. The highest and lowest values of the overall burnout questionnaire and its subdimensions are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Scoring Range of Occupational Burnout Scale

	Minimum score	Maximum score	Number of questions
Total Burnout	0	88	22
Emotional Exhaustion	0	36	9
Depersonalisation	0	20	5
Personal accomplishment	0	32	8

Ergin (1992) investigated the reliability of the scale using two methods. The first method involved calculating the scale's internal consistency. The internal consistency coefficients, determined through Cronbach's Alpha, for the dataset were as follows: Emotional exhaustion exhibited a coefficient of 0.83, Depersonalization measured at 0.65, and Personal accomplishment registered a coefficient of 0.72. Additionally, a secondary approach involved evaluating reliability utilizing the test-retest method. In this context, 99 participants were re-engaged 2-4 weeks after the initial assessment. The test-retest reliability coefficients for the scale's subdimensions were established as follows: Emotional exhaustion (0.83), Depersonalization (0.72), and Personal accomplishment (0.67).

4. Results

4.1. Results Related to Demographic Variables

The statistics of demographic variables consist of gender, age, educational level, income status, field of activity of the organizations, total working experience, work experience in the organization. Table 3 summarizes the demographic data of the participants.

According to the gender distribution of the participants, approximately 84% of the participants are male and 16% are female. When the cumulative percentages of the age distribution of the participants are analyzed, it is found that approximately 40% of the participants are under the age of 35 and the majority of them are over the age of 35. When the cumulative percentages of the participants' educational level distribution were analyzed, it was determined that approximately 89% of the participants had a bachelor's degree or higher. In this direction, it can be said that the educational level of the research sample is quite high.

When the cumulative percentages of the income level distribution of the participants are analyzed, it is seen that approximately 26% of the participants have an income below 7000TL, while approximately 74% of the participants have an income above 7000TL. Accordingly, it can be said that the sampled aviation sector employees have an income above Turkey's standards in terms of income in the context of 2020. When the work experience of the participants in their current companies is analyzed, it is seen that approximately 70% of them have not worked in their companies for more than 10 years. In particular, the fact that 55% of the employees working in the aviation sector have been working in their current company for less than 5 years can be expressed as a sign that the sector has a high labor turnover rate. Looking at the total work experience of the participants, it is understood that 23.3% of them have a total of 21-50 years of work experience in their business life. Finally, it is seen that 67.8% of the participants operate in airline businesses, 11.9% in ground handling services, 9.9% in the education field of the sector and 10.4% in airport businesses.

Table 3: Demographic Variable Summary

Variables	Percentage	
	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender		
Male	84.2	84.2
Female	15.8	100.0
Age Distribution		
18 to 23	3.0	3.0
24 to 29	16.3	19.3
30 to 35	21.3	40.6
36 to 41	23.8	64.4
42 to 47	15.3	79.7
48 and over	20.3	100.0
Education Status		
High School	1.5	1.5
Associate degree	8.9	10.4
Undergraduate	59.4	69.8
Postgraduate	30.2	100.0
Income Status		
0-2500 TL	5.4	5.4
2501-4000 TL	7.9	13.4

4001-5500 TL	11.4	24.8
5501-7000 TL	1.0	25.7
7001-8500 TL	18.8	44.6
8501 TL and over	55.4	100.0
Work Experience in the Current Company		
0-1 year	17.3	17.3
2-5 year	37.6	55.0
6-9 year	15.3	70.3
10-13 year	12.4	82.7
14-50 year	17.3	100.0
Fields of Activity of Current Companies		
Airline	67.8	67.8
Ground Handling	11.9	79.7
Education	9.9	89.6
Airport Business	10.4	100.0
Total Working Experience		
0 to 3	14.4	14.4
4 to 8	21.8	36.1
9 to 14	22.3	58.4
15 to 20	18.3	76.7
21 to 50	23.3	100.0

4.2. Results of Reliability and Validity

The reliability level of all statements in the questionnaire of the study was determined as 0,833. In addition, the study's dependent and independent variables were analyzed for their reliability. The reliability levels of the dimensions of the independent variable of the study, occupational burnout, are as follows: 88% for emotional burnout, 75% for personal accomplishment, 82% for Depersonalization. The reliability levels of the sub-dimensions of the dependent variable job satisfaction were determined as 90% for intrinsic satisfaction and 88% for extrinsic satisfaction, respectively. Since the reliability levels of the scales used in the questionnaire are above 0.60 (Kalaycı, 2014: 322), it can be accepted that the scales are reliable for the research sample. The results of the reliability analyses for each dimension can be seen in the table below (Table 4).

When the confirmatory factor analysis results of the scales are examined, it is seen that the fit indices obtained are $\chi^2/df=1.51$, CFI=0.95, GFI=0.89, RMSEA=0.050 for burnout and $\chi^2/df=2.40$, CFI=0.91, GFI=0.85, RMSEA=0.084 for job satisfaction. Table 4 shows the reliability and validity levels of the scales.

Table 4: Reliability and Validity Results of the Scales

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha Values (α)	Validity Values of Variables	KMO and Bartlett's Test
All Questions (42 questions)	.833	-	.891 (0.00<0.05)
Intrinsic Satisfaction (12 questions)	.895	$\chi^2/df=2.40$ CFI=.91	
Extrinsic Satisfaction (8 questions)	.878	GFI= .85 RMSEA= .084	
Emotional Burnout (9 questions)	.880	$\chi^2/df = 1.51$	
Personal accomplishment (8 questions)	.744	CFI= .95	
Depersonalization (5 questions)	.816	GFI= .89 RMSEA= .050	

The χ^2/df ratio obtained as a result of this study indicates good fit for burnout ($0 \leq \chi^2/df \leq 2$) and acceptable fit for job satisfaction ($2 < \chi^2/df \leq 5$) (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003; Meydan & Şeşen, 2011). It can be said that the comparative fit index is within the range of acceptable values ($90 < CFI \leq 95$) for burnout and job

satisfaction (Kline, 2005; Sutha, 2019: 186). It can be said that the goodness-of-fit index is within the range of acceptable values ($0.85 < GFI \leq 0.89$) for burnout and job satisfaction (Meydan & Şeşen, 2011; Savcı, 2017) and finally, the square root of the mean square error of approximation fit index is considered to be acceptable values ($0.05 < RMSEA \leq 0.10$) for burnout and job satisfaction (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003; Sutha, 2019). In the light of the data above, it can be said that all of the validity values of the variables are within acceptable fit values.

When the results of the KMO Bartlets sphericity test in Table 5 are analysed, it is seen that the sample collected within the scope of the research is sufficient.

Table 5: Sphericity Test Analysis Results (Kmo & Barlett’s Test)

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.891
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	5970.294
	df	1128
	Sig.	.000

4.3. Results on Testing the Research Hypotheses

When the correlation results between the variables were analyzed, it was found that there was a statistically significant negative relationship between emotional burnout and intrinsic satisfaction and a statistically significant negative relationship with extrinsic satisfaction at 0.01 level of significance. Table 6 shows the detailed results of this analyses.

Table 6: Correlation Analyses Results

Variables	Average	Standard Deviation	Intrinsic Satisfaction	Extrinsic Satisfaction	Emotional Burnout	Depersonalization	Personal accomplishment
Intrinsic Satisfaction	3.9278	.75478	1				
Extrinsic Satisfaction	3.4759	.96113	.822**	1			
Emotional Burnout	2.9631	.92075	-.450**	-.430**	1		
Depersonalization	2.5238	.95362	-.373**	-.315**	.817**	1	
Personal accomplishment	3.8453	.57266	.618**	.496**	-.231**	-.219**	1

*n=202; Intensity of the relationship $0,70 < R_{XY} \leq 1$ Strong, $0,40 < R_{XY} < 0,70$ Medium, $0 < R_{XY} < 0,40$ Low**p<0.01

4.3.1. Results of Regression Analysis

Regression analyses were performed to test the effect of occupational burnout of the employees in the aviation sector on the sub-dimensions of job satisfaction. As a result of the regression analysis, when the ANOVA a analysis results were examined, it was determined that each regression model was significant. The detailed analysis obtained is given in Table 7.

Table 7: Regression Analyses Results

Independent Variable (X)	Dependent Variable Intrinsic Satisfaction (Constant Value=1.955)				
	Coefficient (β)	Standard Error	Beta	t	p
Emotional Burnout (X1)	-,288	,073	-,352	-3,948	,000
Depersonalization (X2)	,027	,070	,034	,378	,706
Personal accomplishment	,718	,069	,545	10,351	,000
Adjusted R²	,475 (p<0.00)				
Independent Variable (X)	Dependent variable Extrinsic Satisfaction (Constant Value=4.362)				
	Coefficient (β)	Standard Error	Beta	t	p
Emotional Burnout	-,474	,104	-,454	-4,572	,000
Depersonalization	,150	,100	,149	1,506	,134
Personal accomplishment	,712	,098	,424	7,241	,000
Adjusted R²	,349 (p<0.00)				

*p<0,05 level is significant.

As a result of the analysis, it can be said that occupational burnout has an effect on job satisfaction since the hypotheses related to model significance are supported and the model is significant. Secondly, when we look at the R² explanatory coefficients that should be considered for the significance of the coefficients, it is seen

that they are significant (intrinsic satisfaction $R^2= 48\%$; extrinsic satisfaction $R^2= 35\%$, respectively). Considering the significance of the coefficients:

- The coefficient of the effect of emotional burnout, one of the sub-dimensions of the burnout, on intrinsic satisfaction and extrinsic satisfaction, two of the sub-dimensions of job satisfaction, is significant ($.000 < 0.05$).
- The coefficient for the effect of Depersonalization, one of the sub-dimensions of burnout, on intrinsic satisfaction and extrinsic satisfaction, two of the sub-dimensions of job satisfaction, is insignificant (intrinsic satisfaction $.706 < 0.05$, extrinsic satisfaction $.134 < 0.05$, respectively).
- The effect coefficient of sense of personal accomplishment, one of the sub-dimensions of burnout, on intrinsic satisfaction and extrinsic satisfaction, two of the sub-dimensions of job satisfaction, is significant ($.000 < 0.05$).

Therefore, occupational burnout explains approximately 48% of intrinsic satisfaction, one of the sub-dimensions of job satisfaction, and the remaining 52% is explained by other variables. A one-unit increase in the level of emotional burnout of the employees causes a decrease of $-.288$ units in their intrinsic satisfaction, while a one-unit increase in their level of personal accomplishment causes an increase of $.718$ units in their intrinsic satisfaction.

Thus, as a result of the regression analysis;

An equation such as $Y = 1.995 - 0,288 * X1 + 0.718 * X3$ was formed.

Similarly, occupational burnout explains approximately 35% of extrinsic satisfaction, one of the sub-dimensions of job satisfaction. The remaining 65% is explained by other variables. A one-unit increase in the level of emotional burnout of the employees causes a decrease of $-.474$ units in their extrinsic satisfaction, while a one-unit increase in their level of personal accomplishment causes an increase of $.712$ units in their extrinsic satisfaction.

Thus, as a result of regression analysis;

An equation such as $Y = 4.362 - 0,474 * X1 + 0.712 * X3$ was formed.

5. Discussions and Conclusion

This study aims to investigate the impact of occupational burnout levels on job satisfaction among employees working in the aviation sector in Turkey. Data were collected through online and face-to-face questionnaires from white-collar employees who are decision-makers, process designers, and experts in their respective fields. The study analyzed data obtained from the Maslach Burnout Inventory and the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Questionnaire to investigate the relationship between occupational burnout levels and job satisfaction among employees in the aviation sector. This study is unique in the literature due to the limited number of studies on the relationship between burnout and job satisfaction of employees in the aviation sector in Turkey. Additionally, the sample is limited to cabin crew, which further distinguishes it from previous research (Günay, 2016; Tunceli, 2012).

The study found that emotional exhaustion had a negative relationship with both intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction dimensions. Additionally, depersonalization had a negative relationship with both extrinsic and intrinsic satisfaction dimensions, while personal accomplishment had a negative relationship with intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction dimensions. In a study conducted on bank employees, Ünal Alp (2007) examined the relationship between levels of occupational burnout and job satisfaction. The results showed a negative correlation between emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, which are sub-dimensions of occupational burnout, and intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction. Additionally, a significant positive correlation was found between personal accomplishment and intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction. Berber (2011) conducted a study on the relationship between burnout levels and job satisfaction of tower personnel. The study revealed a significant negative relationship between emotional exhaustion and depersonalization dimensions and job satisfaction, and a significant positive relationship with personal accomplishment. In Şahan's (2015) study, the relationship between burnout levels and job satisfaction of personnel working in health centers was examined. The study found a significant relationship between emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, which are sub-dimensions of burnout, and job satisfaction. However, in contrast to our study, it was determined that there was no significant relationship between personal accomplishment and job satisfaction. The study's results align

with previous research in the field, indicating that an increase in occupational burnout among white-collar workers in the aviation sector may lead to a decrease in job satisfaction.

The study found a moderate negative correlation between emotional exhaustion and intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction. This suggests that an increase in emotional exhaustion may lead to a decrease in job satisfaction, and vice versa. In other words, reducing emotional exhaustion may increase job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is achieved when individuals attain their desired goals and expectations from their organization. This, in turn, leads to mental comfort and happiness, ultimately contributing to life satisfaction. Job satisfaction is achieved when individuals attain their desired goals and expectations from their organization. Research suggests that individuals who experience job satisfaction have higher levels of life satisfaction. Conversely, those with low job satisfaction levels tend to have moderate levels of health, while those with high job satisfaction levels tend to have moderate to high levels of health (Güven et al., 2005; Kaya, 2013).

The correlation analysis reveals a negative relationship between depersonalization and intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction. This suggests that an increase in depersonalization will lead to a decrease in job satisfaction, and vice versa. Therefore, it is important to address depersonalization in order to improve employee job satisfaction. Job dissatisfaction occurs when the conditions necessary for job satisfaction are not met. Individuals experiencing job dissatisfaction may become alienated from their job, lose interest in their work, and may not make any effort to improve workplace conditions. They may view their job solely as a means of earning income. If work conditions cannot be improved, employees may become desensitized not only towards their job but also towards their colleagues and environment. Therefore, it is crucial to enhance employee job satisfaction to prevent depersonalization, particularly for service sector businesses. This is due to the principle of inseparability of service, where the service provided and the employees delivering it cannot be evaluated separately (Kaya, 2013; Karadağ, 2013).

The study found a positive moderate relationship between personal accomplishment and intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction. An increase in the personal accomplishment dimension will lead to an increase in employee job satisfaction, or vice versa. In other words, an increase in job satisfaction will lead to an increase in the feeling of personal accomplishment. Herzberg's dual factor theory supports this relationship in the literature. The theory suggests that job satisfaction leads to increased commitment, morale, and motivation among employees, which in turn positively affects their success levels (Akbulut, 2010; Başaran, 2019).

The study found that emotional exhaustion and personal accomplishment, sub-dimensions of occupational burnout, have an impact on job satisfaction among white-collar employees in the aviation sector. However, the depersonalization dimension of occupational burnout does not appear to have an effect on job satisfaction. It was found that an increase in personal accomplishment leads to an increase in job satisfaction, both internally and externally. Job satisfaction has two dimensions: intrinsic satisfaction and extrinsic satisfaction. Intrinsic satisfaction relates to the nature of the job, including achievement, recognition, appreciation, job responsibilities, promotion, and job changes due to promotion. Extrinsic satisfaction, on the other hand, relates to the work environment, including business policies and management, supervision, relationships with managers and subordinates, wages, and working conditions.

Emotional exhaustion is characterized by the intense depletion of physical and emotional resources in individuals, resulting in mental wear and tear, fatigue, lack of energy, and feelings of hopelessness due to emotional overload. In high-stress work environments, white-collar workers may experience exhaustion over time and feel that their abilities are insufficient to meet job requirements. If emotional exhaustion is not addressed, individuals may become isolated. This situation may lead to depersonalization and internal dissatisfaction. Additionally, the mental and physical strain experienced by employees may cause them to question their working conditions, wages, and values in the eyes of senior management, potentially leading to a decrease in external satisfaction. The study's findings suggest that job satisfaction among white-collar employees in the aviation sector decreases as emotional burnout increases, which is consistent with previous research (Leiter and Maslach, 1988; Budak and Sürgevil, 2005; Berber, 2011; Yıldız, 2015; Göktepe, 2016; Sweeney and Summers, 2002).

Personal accomplishment refers to an individual's perception of their success and competence in their job. The study found that as the personal accomplishment levels of white-collar employees in the aviation sector increase, so does their intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction. White-collar workers who perceive themselves as successful and competent in their jobs may experience an increase in intrinsic satisfaction when they perform well. Additionally, an increase in duties and responsibilities may lead to improved working conditions and

higher wages. Therefore, it can be concluded that job satisfaction may increase when an individual feels successful in their role.

Acknowledgement

This paper is based on a Master's thesis titled "Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Occupational Burnout: An Application on the Workers of the Aviation Industry" completed at Dumlupınar University Graduate School of Social Sciences under the supervision of Assoc. Prof. Dr. Müberra YURDAKUL in 2020

Conflicts of Interest

With regard to the publication of this paper, the authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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Cite this article: Yılmaz, O. A. and Yurdakul, M. (2023). The Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Occupational Burnout: A Cross-Sectional Study on Aviation Industry. *Research in Aviation Management*, 3(2), 29-39.

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